

Upgrading of solid recovered fuel (SRF) by dechlorination and catalytic pyrolysis over nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite

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ABSTRACT

Globally increasing concern related to municipal solid waste generation is encouraging research efforts on developing alternative routes to valorize mixed refused wastes. In this way, catalytic pyrolysis is emerging as an interesting and efficient technology due to its great flexibility in terms of feedstock. In the current work, upgrading of a Solid Recovered Fuel (SRF) has been investigated by catalytic pyrolysis over nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite (*n*-ZSM-5), paying special attention to dechlorination effects due to the high Cl content of the raw waste. Thus, pretreatment of the SRF by water washing and mild thermal pre-treatment allows for a significant reduction of the Cl concentration. Regarding the catalytic pyrolysis step, the best conditions correspond with a temperature of 400 °C in the catalyst bed and 0.50 catalyst/SRF mass ratio, which lead to ca. 30 wt.% oil yield (rich in aromatic hydrocarbons) together with 40 wt.% gas yield (rich in C3-C4 olefins). Accordingly, these products could find use as raw chemicals or for the production of advanced fuels. In addition, zeolite reutilization has been tested for several cycles, denoting a progressive modification of the products distribution because of coke deposition. However, an almost total recovery of the *n*-ZSM-5 zeolite catalytic performance is achieved after regeneration by air calcination, affording the production of an oil fraction with a Cl content as low as 40 ppm.

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing production of municipal solid waste (MSW) is currently a major concern all around the world. During the last decades there has been a sustained increase in the worldwide production of this type of urban waste, and the projections estimate an additional 70 % rise by 2050 (Kaza et al., 2018). Most countries are defining management policies to face this problem, mainly focused on prevention, reduction and recycling, within a circular economy strategy (European Commission, 2020). However, because of management inefficiencies, not every waste can be destined to reuse or recycling, and a significant proportion unfortunately still ends accumulating in landfills. Hence, alternative uses must be found to prevent or minimize this situation, like the production of solid recovered fuel (SRF). SRF is typically defined as solid fuel prepared from non-hazardous waste to be utilized for energy recovery in incineration and co-incineration plants. For these uses, SRF needs to meet the classification and specification requirements laid down in specific standards (*DIN EN 15357: Solid recovered fuels - Terminology, definitions and descriptions*, 2011). The preparation of SRF from raw waste encompasses processing, homogenization, and upgrading steps to obtain a quality acceptable for an 'energy product' that can be traded amongst producers and users. In this way, SRF comprises a wide variety of theoretically recyclable materials that are recovered in forms that made their recycling an unsound option. Indeed, SRF origin ranges from MSW to sewage sludge or shredded tires, so depending on the source it can be considered even partly renewable because of its biogenic content. It typically consists of highly calorific rejected materials, such as plastics, textiles, wood, and elastomers (Garcés et al., 2016).

Co-firing SRF in energy production units, even at reduced thermal shares, is the traditional waste-to-energy technology employed to valorize this kind of material (Dunnu et al., 2010). The power plant sector is adopting the co-firing of biomass and SRF with coal in an effort to reduce its environmental impact and costs (Iacovidou et al., 2018). However, when considering not only waste-to-energy but also waste-to-chemicals routes, other technologies gain interest for the SRF valorization. Pyrolysis has thus received an increasing attention due to its simplicity, short operation times and versatility to

admit a wide range of waste materials as feedstock, including biomass residues (K N et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020; Yildiz and Prins, 2023) or plastic wastes (Klaimy et al., 2021; Yansaneh and Zein, 2022). Pyrolysis involves the thermal decomposition of carbon-based materials under inert atmosphere at mild-high temperature, in the range of 400-700 °C, typically yielding three product fractions: liquid (oil), solid (char), and gas (non-condensable gaseous fraction mainly constituted by CO, CO₂, H₂, and C₁-C₄ hydrocarbons).

In recent years, a great interest has arisen for the possible use of the oil and gas fractions derived from the pyrolysis of residues as a source of both liquid fuels and chemicals (Hu and Gholizadeh, 2020; Urrutia et al., 2022). It is generally accepted that low temperature pyrolysis favors oil formation and the production of long-chain hydrocarbons, while high temperature pyrolysis leads to an increase in the gas production (Hernando et al., 2018). Likewise, pyrolysis products properties can be considerably improved by the incorporation of catalysts promoting transformations such as cracking, decarboxylation, decarbonylation, and condensation reactions, leading to upgraded fuels, or increasing the selectivity towards valuable products, such as aromatics, and phenolics (Hernando et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2022).

The use of acid catalysts in the pyrolytic process of plastics, like ZSM-5 and H-Y zeolites, significantly alters the product distribution. These materials present a high cracking activity, allowing the conversion of waxes and other heavy components into oil and gases (Ma et al., 2017; Marino et al., 2022; Miskolczi et al., 2017). Additionally, by tuning the catalyst properties, as well as the operating conditions, it is possible to drive the products distribution to obtain high yields of pyrolysis liquids that may be suitable for both fuels and chemicals industries. From an energy point-of-view, the resultant oil can be utilized as an energy carrier for co-processing in traditional oil refinery schemes (Lindfors et al., 2023). Likewise, such a catalytic pyrolysis liquid might find use as a valuable raw material for the petrochemical industry (Singh, 2022; Yildiz and Prins, 2023). However, the use of SRF as feedstock for thermochemical processes like gasification and pyrolysis process has been relatively little investigated (Han et al., 2022; Tokmurzin et al., 2022). The heterogeneous origin of SRF typically implies the

presence of halogens in its composition, mainly in the form of chlorine contained in plastic wastes. This hinders the valorization of SRF via pyrolysis, as it introduces concerns about corrosion issues in downstream processing of the resultant oil in a traditional refinery scheme (Al-Moubaraki and Obot, 2021). Therefore, the efficient and safe removal of chlorine to an acceptable concentration for refinery co-feeding remains a challenge. Depending on the type of residue and the halogens concentration, it is often necessary to pretreat the feedstocks to reduce the concentration of these undesired compounds in the final products. In this way, the investigation of dechlorination strategies during pyrolysis has been basically focused on Cl-containing plastic residues (Hubáček et al., 2022; Shen et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2013). Likewise, Genuino and co-workers provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of washing pre-treatment methods for reducing inorganic halogen concentrations in plastics (Genuino et al., 2022). In other recent study, PVC-containing WEEE residues were subjected to thermal pre-treatment at 350 °C under an inert atmosphere, leading to the removal of a significant portion (87%) of the chlorine in the PVC (Marino et al., 2022). However, to the best of our knowledge, no articles have been so far published on the catalytic pyrolysis of SRF materials, neither on analyzing dechlorination strategies by using pre-treatments of such waste-derived materials.

In this context, the aim of the current work is to assess the potential of catalytic pyrolysis for the upgrading of a real SRF feedstock, using a nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite as catalyst, while paying special attention to dechlorination effects. ZSM-5 zeolite has been selected for this study, as a representative acid zeolite, because of its excellent cracking properties, high aromatization activity and easy availability from commercial suppliers. Accordingly, using an exemplary SRF sample, this study reports the influence of the pre-treatment of the feedstock by washing and mild thermal processing, as well as the optimization of the operation conditions in the catalytic step, focusing not only on product distribution but also on the Cl fate among the different fractions. Finally, the reusability of the catalyst has also been assessed.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. SRF characterization

The feedstock used in this work is a Solid Recovered Fuel (SRF) provided by *Reciclados Palancia Belcaire* (Spain) mainly consisting of high-energy fractions derived from typical municipal solid waste (MSW). This waste has been manually segregated into the different fractions to obtain the following approximate composition: 55, 26, 17, and 2 wt%, for wood and other organic, plastics, paper and cupboard, and others, respectively. This estimation is in good agreement with the typical values that can be found in literature for MSW (Kumar and Samadder, 2017). Previously to its valorization in the pyrolytic reactor, the SRF was grounded in a cutting mill and sieved to a particle size of 1-2 mm. Thereafter, it was stored at 90 °C for drying and avoiding humidity uptake. For characterization, a proximate analysis of the prepared SRF was carried out to determine ash (ISO 18122:2015), volatile matter (ISO 18123:2015) and fixed carbon (by difference) contents. Ash was calculated by calcination (air flow, 80 mL/min) using a thermobalance (Netzsch, STA 449 F3) from ambient temperature to 550 °C (10 °C /min), whereas volatile matter content was obtained using the same thermogravimetric equipment heating the sample up to 900 °C (10 °C/min) in argon flow (80 mL/min). SRF elemental analysis was performed to determine C, H, N, S contents in an organic elemental analyzer (ThermoScientific, Flash 2000), while O content was calculated as follows (Eq. 1):

$$O \text{ (wt. \%)} = 100 - C \text{ (wt. \%)} - H \text{ (wt. \%)} - N \text{ (wt. \%)} - S \text{ (wt. \%)} - \text{Ashes (wt. \%)} \quad (1)$$

In order to evaluate the presence of halogenated compounds in the SRF, active oxidative decomposition (AOD) technique with a bomb calorimeter (IKA) was applied to the waste according with EPA 5050 and EPA 9056A standards. The resulting solution was analyzed by ion chromatography (IC) with a Metrohm IC 930 Compact IC Flex chromatograph equipped with a Metrosep A Supp 7-150/4.0 column, A Supp 5 Guard/4.0 as pre-column, and module MSM II as suppressor. Sodium

carbonate solution (3.6 mM) was employed as effluent and a multi-component standard of 25 ppm (F^- , Cl^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} and SO_4^{2-} , Reagecon) was used to calibrate the ion chromatograph. Samples were analyzed by triplicate to assess the error in terms of standard deviation (data shown in tables) or error bars (data shown in figures).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping were carried out in a JEOL JSM-7900F microscope with an accelerating voltage of 15.0 kV and ULTIM Max 170 (Oxford Instruments) as EDS detector. Char surface morphology was analyzed by SEM images, whereas the elemental distribution and composition, specifically Cl, C and Na, were determined on EDS mapping.

2.2. SRF pre-conditioning

Different conditioning pretreatments were applied to SRF in order to reduce its halogen content. The first one consisted of a washing step with Mili-Q water, by means of two consecutive runs of 30 min at room temperature under stirring with H_2O /SRF mass ratio of 20. Washing water was collected and its halogen concentration was determined by IC as previously explained, using this value to determine the washing efficiency. The second pretreatment consisted of a heating step at moderate temperature, and it was performed using the washed SRF and an inert atmosphere of nitrogen (50 mL/min). The temperature was increased from 20 to 300 °C with a ramp of 10 °C/min and a final isotherm step of 30 min. After completion of both pretreatments, the final SRF was stored at 90 °C to avoid ambient water adsorption. The generated pre-conditioned residues were analyzed using the same analytical techniques as for raw SRF (see section 2.1).

2.3. Pyrolysis experiments

Thermal and catalytic pyrolysis experiments were carried out in a stainless steel fixed-bed reactor (internal diameter 15.1 mm, length 380 mm) with upstream flow. Fig. 1 depicts a schematic representation of the set-up. The reactor consisted of two zones, independently heated by two different electrical furnaces, and controlled by K-type thermocouples: thermal (lower) and catalytic

(upper) zones. In a typical experiment, SRF sample (7 g) was introduced into the thermal part. In the case of catalytic experiments, a commercial nanocrystalline zeolite (*n*-ZSM-5, Si/Al=42, Clariant, ref. HCZP90) was located in the upper zone at an appropriate height with the help of stainless-steel tube, nets and quartz wool. A detailed characterization of this ZSM-5 catalyst has been earlier reported (Artillo et al., 2023) and most relevant properties are summarized in Table S1.

Figure 1. Experimental set-up for the SRF thermal and catalytic pyrolysis experiments.

The experiments were performed using 100 mL/min of N₂ as sweep gas, which was fed by a mass flow controller (Bronkhorst, El-Flow) under atmospheric pressure. Temperature in the thermal zone in all tests was fixed at 550 °C, whereas the influence of catalytic step temperature was studied by working at three different levels (400, 450 and 500 °C). Also, the catalyst/SRF mass ratio was varied, adjusting the amount of catalyst in the fixed bed, to the following values: 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75. Additionally, reusability tests of the catalyst were also performed (up to four cycles). The spent zeolite after 4 uses was subjected to a regeneration treatment by calcination in air at 550 °C (2 h, 10 °C/min heating ramp), aiming at burning off the organic deposits formed on the catalyst.

As the temperature of the thermal zone was progressively increased, pyrolysis reactions started to occur and the so-formed gases and volatiles components were swept by a N₂ stream, being passed through the catalyst bed. Different product fractions were collected: waxes, oil, aqueous phase, gases, char (non-pyrolyzed fraction of the fed SRF) and spent catalyst. The condensable fraction of the reactor outlet was collected by means of a train of connected bottles: the first one was immersed into a hot water container (to limit the condensation only to heavy compounds, herein denoted as waxes), the next two bottles were immersed in an ice-water bath at 0 °C to condensate lighter compounds (pooled fraction denoted as oil), and the resultant gas stream was finally bubbled through water at 0 °C to capture the released HCl. The HCl-free non-condensable gases were then quantified by using a home-made totalizer. Upon completion of the experiment, char and catalyst were recovered from both reactor zones for further analysis.

2.4. Products analysis

In non-catalytic pyrolysis experiments, also denoted as thermal pyrolysis, waxes were produced, being formed by heavy hydrocarbons (>15 carbon atoms). Their chemical composition was determined by using a gas chromatograph (GC, Agilent 8860) equipped with flame ionization detector (FID), DB-5ht column (30 m × 320 µm × 0.1 µm) and helium as carrier gas. Samples were previously dissolved in carbon disulfide with a concentration of 2 wt.% before being introduced into the GC. On the other hand, in the catalytic experiments a liquid fraction was obtained and two phases were clearly identified, one was the so-called oil, which was of organic nature, and the other was an aqueous fraction. They were carefully decanted and separately analyzed using different techniques. Karl-Fischer titration (Mettler-Toledo, V20) was performed to determine the amount of water present in each fraction. The oil chemical composition was analyzed using two gas chromatographic methods: the above-mentioned method for heavy compounds quantification in the waxes fraction, and PIONA (Paraffins, Iso-paraffins, Olefins, Naphtenes and Aromatics) analysis to measure light compounds (<15 carbon atoms). The latter was carried out in a GC-FID chromatograph (Agilent 7890A) with CP-Sil

column PIONA CB (100 m × 250 μm × 0.5 μm) and helium as carrier gas. To that end, the oil fraction was dissolved in carbon disulfide at 2 wt.% and the concentration of each compound was calculated using DHA Standard (PIONA) (Separation Systems, ref. SD-053-001). Elemental analysis was applied for waxes, aqueous and organic fractions, whereas the halogen content was estimated directly by IC (aqueous phase) or indirectly by AOD-IC (waxes and oil).

Gaseous products were quantified with a micro-GC analyzer (Agilent Technologies, 490) equipped with molecular sieve (Molsieve 5 Å), PPQ columns and a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). Helium was used as the carrier gas. The previously calibrated quantified gaseous components were H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆, C₃H₈, C₄H₈, C₄H₁₀, C₅H₁₀ and C₅H₁₂. The content of HCl in the gases was measured by recovering water from the last bubblers condenser and subsequent IC analysis. No nitrogen oxides (NO_x) were detected in the gaseous stream from the pyrolysis tests.

After each experiment, the remaining solid fraction (char) and spent catalysts were recovered and characterized using the same analytical techniques as in the SRF characterization in terms of elemental composition and halogen content (elemental analysis and AOD-IC, respectively). The quantity of carbonaceous deposits, i.e., coke, formed over the zeolite surface was obtained by a controlled calcination in air (80 mL/min) from room temperature to 900 °C (10 °C/min and 30 min as final isotherm) using a Netzsch STA 449 F3 thermobalance to record the weight loss.

Reproducibility of the pyrolysis runs, as well as of the subsequent products analysis, was assessed by performing 3 replicas, hence determining the average error in terms of standard deviation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Pyrolysis of SRF: effect of washing pretreatment and presence of catalyst

Initial approach to SRF pyrolysis is performed evaluating the effect of water-washing during SRF conditioning. Fig. 2 shows images of the different SRFs, whereas Table 1 summarizes the main characterization thereof.

Figure 2. SRF samples: (a) raw, as received; (b) raw, shredded to 1-2 mm particle size; (c) washed with water at rt; and (d) washed with water at rt and thermally pretreated at 300 °C.

Table 1. Proximate and elemental analyses of the different SRF samples, including High Heating Value (HHV) and chlorine content.

SRF treatment	Proximate analysis (wt.%)			Elemental analysis (wt.%) ^a				HHV (MJ/Kg) ^b	Cl (wt.%)
	Volatile	Fixed C	Ash	C	H	N	O		
Raw (shredded)	86.70	4.98	8.32	69.62	10.61	0.86	9.49	35.5	1.10
Washing	89.18	0.73	10.09	69.76	10.99	0.37	7.84	36.2	0.95
Washing + thermal step	86.54	0.00	13.46	69.38	9.42	0.43	6.76	37.0	0.55
Average Error^c	± 2.88	± 1.28	± 0.98	± 0.46	± 0.26	± 0.12	± 0.55	-	± 0.28

^a Sulfur content was negligible in all the cases. ^b Calculated using an empirical correlation (Channiwala and Parikh, 2002).

^c Standard deviations, obtained from repeated measurements and expressed as wt.%.

As it can be observed in Fig. 2a, the selected SRF is composed by different waste components, mainly plastics, paper, and organic matter, showing a high degree of heterogeneity. Shredding helps to homogenize the material (Fig. 2b). After washing with water, insignificant changes can be visualized in the SRF, observing the same degree of matter segregation (Fig. 2c). However, characterization data indicate some relevant differences upon applying this pretreatment (Table 1). Thus, an increase in ashes and volatiles contents can be observed in the washed SRF, with the consequent decrease of the

fixed carbon. This can be attributed to a partial removal of inorganic matter during washing. On the other hand, the pretreatment is also effective in lowering the chlorine content, totalizing a 14% reduction. This effect may be ascribed to the removal of water-soluble chlorides. As previously highlighted, reducing the halogen content, here represented by chlorine species, is essential to minimize corrosion and handling issues in downstream processing of the pyrolysis products, especially in the case of co-refining. Regarding energy content, HHV values are very similar for both samples, indicating an insignificant impact of the washing treatment on this crucial parameter for energy-related applications.

Additionally, in order to analyze the dispersion and nature of inorganic Cl present in the SRF, SEM images of the chars resulting from the pyrolysis process are visualized in Fig. 3, including the corresponding elemental mappings. The char produced from the raw SRF exhibits high heterogeneity, showing aggregates of large sodium chloride crystals, as evidenced by the perfect correspondence between Na and Cl mappings (see also individual images in Fig. S1). Likewise, a slight association can also be inferred between chlorine and calcium (indicative of the presence of CaCl_2) and, with a lower intensity, chlorine and carbon (indicative of the presence of Cl in the carbonaceous matrix of the char). On the other hand, the char coming from washed SRF is more homogeneous in morphology and composition, displaying a higher dispersion of the analyzed elements. In this case, NaCl crystals are no longer detected, confirming the effectiveness of the washing pretreatment for their removal.

Figure 3. SEM images with elemental mapping of chars from the pyrolysis of (a) raw SRF and (b) washed SRF.

Taking into account these first considerations, thermal pyrolysis (in the absence of catalyst) of raw and washed SRF was carried out at 550 °C. As shown in Table 2, there are no large differences between raw and washed SRF in terms of fraction yields, being waxes the predominant one with values over 60 wt.% in both experiments. Pyrolytic waxes consist mostly of long chain hydrocarbons (*n*-paraffins and α -olefins) with more than fifteen carbon atoms. The production of gases is also very close in both tests and limited to a relatively small quantity (ca. 10 wt.%), as corresponds to a thermal (non-catalytic) pyrolytic process. The composition of such gas fraction is similar in both SRF samples as well, being CO₂ the main component. However, in terms of chlorine concentration in waxes, a strong reduction is detected upon the washing pretreatment (from 3009 to 2012 ppm), which confirms the benefits of such preconditioning to reduce the Cl loading in the generated waxes.

Table 2. Fraction yields and Cl content in oil/wax obtained in thermal and catalytic pyrolysis of SRF. Operating conditions: 550 °C thermal zone, 450 °C catalytic zone; 0.5 *n*-ZSM-5/SRF mass ratio.

Pyrolysis	SRF treatment	Yield to fractions (wt.%)						Cl content (ppm)
		Char ^a	Waxes	Coke	Oil	Aqueous	Gases	
Thermal	Raw	25.2	62.7	-	-	-	12.1	3009 ^b
	Washed	25.6	64.3	-	-	-	10.1	2012 ^b
Average Error^d		± 1.3	± 2.8	-	-	-	± 1.2	± 328
Catalytic	Raw	23.8	-	1.8	27.0	5.5	42.0	605 ^c
	Washed	21.4	-	2.2	28.7	6.0	41.6	429 ^c
Average Error^d		± 1.4	-	± 0.1	± 0.7	± 0.2	± 1.0	± 56

^a Carbonaceous solid residue of the pyrolysis process, including ashes. ^b Cl content in waxes. ^c Cl content in oil. ^d Standard deviations, determined from repeated tests and expressed as wt.% (yields) and ppm (Cl content).

Raw and washed SRFs were then assayed in the catalytic pyrolysis using the *n*-ZSM-5 zeolite catalyst. Since this material is a nanocrystalline zeolite sample, it shows a relatively high external surface area (Table S1), which is a positive fact for the conversion of bulky components formed during the pyrolysis of the SRF feedstock. As it can be seen in Table 2, the use of an acid zeolite catalyst produces a dramatic change in the obtained products, either for the raw SRF or the washed SRF. Waxes fraction completely disappears in the catalytic process, giving instead rise to the generation of two liquid products: oil (27-

29 wt.%) and aqueous (5.5-6.0 wt.%) phases. The formation of the latter can be interpreted as the consequence of the dehydration activity of the acid catalyst, being related to the oxygen content of the starting material (Table 1). Likewise, there is a sharp enhancement in the production of gases in the catalytic pyrolysis, becoming the main fraction in this case (41-42 wt.%). Finally, a relatively small coke deposition occurs over the catalyst surface, derived from its strong acidity. Other interesting fact is that the use of the zeolite catalyst leads to a dechlorinated oil fraction, showing Cl contents of 605 ppm (raw SRF) and 429 ppm (washed SRF), which are much lower than those of the waxes obtained from the thermal pyrolysis (3009 and 2012 ppm, respectively, Table 2).

Regarding the composition of the gas fractions, whereas in the thermal pyrolysis the main components are CO₂ and CO, in the catalytic process light C3-C4 olefins are predominant (Fig. 4), coming from primary cracking reactions (Wong et al., 2023). Brønsted acidic sites play an important role as proton donors during the catalytic cracking of hydrocarbons (Xian et al., 2021), including plastic decomposition products (Ojha and Vinu, 2015; Serrano et al., 2000), into smaller species. Such Brønsted acidic sites in the *n*-ZSM-5 zeolite originate from protons balancing the negative charges of Si substitution by Al atoms within the crystalline framework.

Figure 4. Gas yields obtained in the thermal and catalytic pyrolysis of washed SRF. Operating conditions: thermal zone temperature = 550 °C, catalytic zone temperature = 450 °C catalytic zone, *n*-ZSM-5/SRF mass ratio = 0.5.

3.2. Optimization of the catalytic pyrolysis step

In order to optimize the performance of the *n*-ZSM-5 catalysts in terms of both products distribution and oil Cl-content, the effect of varying the temperature of the catalyst bed and the zeolite/SRF mass ratio was studied (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Fraction yields in the catalytic pyrolysis of washed SRF: (a) Effect of varying the *n*-ZSM-5/SRF mass ratio (catalytic zone temperature = 450 °C); (b) Effect of varying the temperature in the catalytic zone (catalyst/SRF mass ratio = 0.50).

As depicted in Fig. 5a, oil yield decreases significantly as zeolite/SRF ratio is increased, favouring instead an enhancement of the gases production, in line with a higher extent of severe cracking reactions. Likewise, the formation of the aqueous phase is clearly enhanced at higher zeolite/SRF ratios, which is consistent with a higher deoxygenation catalytic activity through dehydration reactions. As to the effect of temperature in the catalytic zone of the reactor (Fig. 5b), similar trends are observed, with lower oil and higher gas yields as the temperature is increased, but less pronounced than in the case of the catalyst/SRF ratio. Moreover, the production of the aqueous phase tends to decrease with the temperature, effect which is opposite to that of the catalyst loading. A similar trend is observed for the coke yield, being higher as the zeolite/SRF ratio is augmented but showing a reduction effect when increasing the temperature. In overall, the highest oil yield (ca. 40 wt.%, referred to initial SRF) is achieved for both the lowest zeolite/SRF ratio and the lowest temperature.

Regarding the composition of the produced oil, different hydrocarbon families have been detected and quantified by PIONA analysis: paraffins, iso-paraffins, aromatics, naphthenes and olefins (Fig. S2). In all the cases, the predominant group corresponds with aromatic hydrocarbons, most of them monoaromatic species such as benzene, toluene, xylenes or alkylbenzenes, among others (Table S2). The aromatics concentration in the oil is enhanced when both the catalyst/SRF ratio and the temperature are increased, reaching a maximum value of about 85.5 wt.% (68.5, 10.7, 1.6 and 3.7 % for mono-aromatics, naphthenes, indanes and indenes, respectively). Under these conditions, both toluene and xylenes are the predominant compounds, which brings forward the promising applications of the obtained oils as a source of chemicals. Just slight variations can be observed for the rest of the families.

As expected, the char yield is approximately the same in both series of experiments since the temperature of the thermal zone has been kept constant. With respect to the gaseous components (Fig. S3), decarbonylation does not seem to be affected in a high extent by varying the zeolite/SRF ratio or the temperature, with an almost constant CO yield (c.a. 2.5 wt.%), whereas the CO₂ production is slightly enhanced at low temperature and catalyst loading. When it comes to the distribution of light paraffins and olefins (C3-C4 valuable gaseous compounds), the largest yields are achieved for both the highest catalyst loading and temperature, as corresponds to the promotion of severe cracking reactions over the *n*-ZSM-5 zeolite.

The overall product distribution in terms of carbon atom numbers (Fig. S4) exhibits two main contributions for all the catalytic pyrolysis tests. The first peak, placed at C3-C4, corresponds with the products coming from primary cracking reactions, which mainly consists of light olefins. The second peak is located at C8, being associated to hydrocarbons formed from light olefins by means of the oligomerization/cyclization/aromatization pathway (Artillo et al., 2023; Miandad et al., 2019), which produces aromatics as major component in the oil fraction. Certainly, the high abundance of light olefins and aromatics in the gas and oil fractions, respectively, obtained in the catalytic pyrolysis of SRF opens the way for an application not only in the production of fuels but also of valuable raw chemicals.

Fig. 6 illustrates the distributions of chlorine among the different fractions obtained of the pyrolysis process, together with the resultant Cl concentration in the respective oils (insert). As shown, chlorine is accumulated mainly in two fractions: char and aqueous phase. Ashes, which constitute a large part of the produced char (approx. 10 wt.% of starting SRF, Table 1), may be acting as a trap for chlorine, as previously reported (Marino et al., 2022). However, a possible contribution of the carbonaceous matter within the char in the Cl capture process should not be neglected.

Figure 6. Chlorine distribution in the catalytic pyrolysis of washed SRF: (a) Effect of varying the *n*-ZSM-5/SRF mass ratio (catalytic zone temperature = 450 °C); (b) Effect of varying the temperature in the catalytic zone (*n*-ZSM-5/SRF mass ratio = 0.50). Insert: Cl content in the oil fraction.

On the other hand, the generation of an aqueous phase facilitates the retention of the HCl released during the thermal and catalytic pyrolysis steps, reaching percentages similar to those of char. Consequently, the oil phase displays a relatively small Cl content. This result confirms that the catalyst promotes the formation of HCl that is captured within the resultant aqueous phase. In fact, it has been previously reported that the major pyrolysis gaseous products of PVC at temperature > 400 °C include hydrogen chloride (Pan et al., 2021), whereas PVC is expected to be an important contributor to the Cl content in a typical MSW-derived SRF. In addition, the spent catalyst samples have been also analyzed by AOD-IC technique, resulting in very small Cl contents. In conclusion, char and the aqueous phase act as effective halogen traps, accumulating most of the Cl initially contained in the washed SRF material.

Chlorine concentration in the oil is reduced when increasing the catalyst loading (from 545 to 190 ppm for 0.25 and 0.75 *n*-ZSM-5/SRF ratios), which is also a confirmation of the zeolite dechlorination activity since it provokes the formation of additional HCl being retained in the aqueous phase. In contrast, the temperature of the catalytic step possesses a detrimental effect as its variation from 400 to 500 °C causes an enhancement of the oil Cl content. This fact suggests that the Cl-containing species coming out from the thermal pyrolysis zone are relatively heavy compounds, which are more retained/adsorbed on the zeolite surface at lower temperatures, thus favouring their catalytic transformation giving rise to the release of additional HCl.

In view of these results, we selected as the best conditions to continue the investigation a temperature of 400 °C for the catalytic step and a 0.50 catalyst/SRF mass ratio. Although the oil yield under such conditions is not the highest (Fig.5), the Cl content in the oil fraction is the lowest (177 ppm, Fig.6b), which is the key issue in terms of oil quality. Furthermore, the use of the lowest temperature would also be beneficial from the economic point of view reducing the energy consumption.

3.3. Effect of thermal pretreatment of SRF

Though the resultant oil from the catalytic pyrolysis of SRF can achieve a Cl content as low as 177 ppm working at 400 °C and 0.50 catalyst/SRF ratio (Fig. 6b), this value should be even lower for a more convenient use of this liquid fraction for refinery co-processing. Thus, an additional study focused on a second preconditioning step of the SRF has been performed, previously to its feeding into the pyrolysis reactor. In this case, a thermal pre-treatment at moderate temperature (300 °C) under N₂ atmosphere was applied to the already washed SRF. This second pretreatment seeks for the thermal decomposition of remaining PVC. This polymer is known to be pyrolyzed through two main stages, a first one at 200-360 °C and a second one at 360-550 °C (Pan et al., 2021). The first stage is attributed to the dechlorination of PVC, releasing hydrogen chloride. The second one consists of the breakage of the remaining polyethene chain, forming aromatics and low amounts of Cl-containing compounds. Thus, a thermogravimetric analysis performed on the raw SRF indicated the presence of a significant

weight loss in the range 200-360 °C, confirming the presence of some amount of PVC (Fig. 7). For the washed SRF the peak corresponding to PVC is still present. However, when the additional step of thermal pretreatment at 300 °C is applied, the peak completely disappears. This is corroborated by the Cl content of the washed + thermally treated SRF shown in Table 1, that it is about 58 % of that in the washed SRF (0.55 vs. 0.95 wt.%).

Figure 7. TGA in argon of SRF according to the applied pretreatment: none, washing, combination of washing plus heating at 300 °C (thermal).

A catalytic pyrolysis experiment performed on this doubly preconditioned SRF, under the selected operation conditions (400 °C and 0.50 catalyst/SRF ratio), led to a significant reduction in terms of Cl concentration in the pyrolysis oil, achieving a value of 141 ppm (from 177 ppm). Furthermore, no relevant changes in the global yields to the different fractions were observed, indicating that the thermal pre-treatment does not alter the pyrolysis outcome. Hence, this strategy helps in maximizing the dechlorination effect during the catalytic pyrolysis of SRF.

3.4. Reusability of the catalyst

The stability of the catalyst is a key issue to achieve a productive and cost-effective pyrolysis process. Hence, the robustness of the *n*-ZSM-5 zeolite was evaluated in a reutilization experiment consisting of four consecutive reaction cycles under the selected operation conditions. The catalyst was placed in the catalytic bed of the reactor and was kept there for four pyrolysis cycles, loading new washed and

thermally pretreated SRF in the thermal zone in each run. Only a minor catalyst sample for coke characterization was extracted in between consecutive uses, adjusting accordingly the amount of fed SRF to keep a constant 0.5 catalyst/SRF mass ratio. Fig. 8 includes the results in terms of fraction yields, chlorine distribution and oil composition obtained in the reutilization tests.

Figure 8. Reusability of the n-ZSM-5 catalyst in the pyrolysis of washed and thermally pretreated SRF: (a) Fraction yields, (b) oil composition determined by PIONA analysis, and (c) chlorine distribution referred to initial content in the SRF and oil Cl content (insert). Operating conditions: thermal zone temperature = 550 °C, catalytic zone temperature = 400 °C, n-ZSM-5/SRF = 0.5 mass ratio.

In terms of fraction yields, it can be seen that the zeolite maintains a great part of its catalytic activity in repeated uses. Thus, no evident formation of solid waxes is observed even after the 4th reusing test in contrast with what occurs in the thermal pyrolysis, i.e., in the absence of catalyst. However, a slight but constant evolution of the production of the different fractions can be observed: the oil yield is progressively increased (from 29.2 to 38.0 wt.%), accompanied by a concomitant amelioration of the yields of both gases and aqueous phase (Fig. 8a). This trend is indicative of a partial catalyst deactivation, affecting mainly to severe cracking and dehydration reactions, responsible for the production of the gases and aqueous phase, respectively. Likewise, the oil composition suffers a remarkable change, with a notable reduction in the production of aromatics and the corresponding increase in the presence of paraffins and isoparaffins, as determined in the PIONA analysis (Fig. 8b). Likewise, the carbon distribution reflects the growing appearance of heavier hydrocarbons, as a direct consequence of a reduced cracking activity (Fig. S5). Finally, the composition of the resultant gas also shows an enrichment in heavier C5 compounds together with a reduction of light C3-C4 olefins (Fig. S6). Considered all together, there is clear evidence of the modification of the catalyst behavior due to coke deposition, which is in agreement with the continuous rise observed in the coke yield (Fig. 8a). In this way, thermogravimetric analyses of the spent catalysts (Fig. 9) exhibit two main peaks at different temperatures (c.a. 300 °C and 500 - 550 °C, respectively), which denotes the presence of different types of carbonaceous deposits. The high temperature peak is detected already in the first reaction cycle and can be linked to the formation of carbonaceous matter strongly retained within the zeolite micropores. The weight loss associated to this peak is about 5.4 wt.% for the first reaction cycle and increases to 11 wt.% in the fourth one, both values being referred to the zeolite weight. These data are lower than the theoretical value corresponding to the filling of the zeolite micropores by organic matter (about 12-14 wt.%), denoting that there is still some space available within the zeolite crystals. Interestingly, the low temperature TGA peak appears mainly after the 3rd reusing cycle, representing up to about 20 wt.% of the zeolite weight for the last cycle. As this value is quite higher than the one

corresponding to the micropore filling, it can be concluded that it is originated by coke deposits located and growing over the external surface, i.e., around the zeolite nanocrystals.

Figure 9. TGA in air of reutilized and regenerated *n*-ZSM-5 catalyst. Operating conditions: washed and thermally pretreated SRF, 550 °C thermal zone, 400 °C catalytic zone, 0.5 *n*-ZSM-5/SRF mass ratio.

The spent zeolite was subjected to a regeneration treatment by air calcination to eliminate carbonaceous deposits. As shown in Fig. 9, the regenerated zeolite recovers the thermogravimetric profile of the fresh zeolite, indicating that coke is completely removed during the calcination process. It must be noted that in between uses (from 1st to 4th) the catalyst is not calcined, so accumulated coke can be observed in the TGA corresponding to the recovered catalysts. It is upon the regeneration treatment (sample denoted as 'Reg') when the spent zeolite is calcined and the coke fraction completely disappears.

The use of this regenerated catalyst in a new SRF pyrolysis experiment resulted essentially in the same catalytic performance of the fresh material, either in terms of yields to the different phases (Fig. 8a and b) or in products distribution (Fig. 8b-S5-S6).

As to the chlorine distribution, the first point to be highlighted is the quite lower proportion of Cl captured in the aqueous phase with this SFR feedstock in comparison with the non-thermally treated SRF, which in turn provokes an enhancement in the share of the halogen trapped in the char fraction

(up to 80 – 90 %). This important variation evidences that a great part of the Cl-containing species, mainly those being most susceptible to give rise to HCl release, are eliminated during the mild thermal pretreatment at 300 °C. On the other hand, the Cl content in the aqueous phase decreases during the reutilization experiments (Fig. 8c), in particular for the 3rd and 4th cycles. In the same way, Cl content does not increase in the oil phase during the reusing tests, being also significantly reduced in the last two cycles. These findings suggest that the coke deposits built over the external surface of the zeolite crystals (second peak in the TGA) might be acting also as Cl traps. Finally, the oil dechlorination remains very high after catalyst regeneration, producing an oil with a low Cl content (below 50 ppm).

4. Conclusions

In this work, the valorization of SRF through catalytic pyrolysis has been demonstrated as a promising route to convert this type of waste-derived fuel into valuable compounds (especially considering gaseous and aromatic hydrocarbons). Water washing and thermal treatments applied to SRF, together with the use of a nanocrystalline ZSM-5 zeolite as catalyst, lead to the production of low-chlorine oil with potential use in refinery co-processing.

The best conditions among those evaluated are a temperature of 400 °C in the catalytic zone and 0.50 catalyst/SRF mass ratio. In this way, Cl content in the oil can be minimized to 141 ppm, while achieving ca. 30 wt.% oil yield together with 40 wt.% gas yield. The oil fractions is rich in aromatic hydrocarbons (with xylenes and toluene as major components), while the gas stream presents a high proportion of C3-C4 olefins. Furthermore, the catalyst can be reutilized in several consecutive pyrolysis cycles keeping the activity, though with a progressive modification of the products distribution because of coke deposition. However, an almost total regeneration of the *n*-ZSM-5 zeolite can be achieved by means of calcination in air at 550 °C.

Regarding the Cl fate, the char fraction and the aqueous phase generated from the occurrence of dehydration reactions acts as effective halogen traps, accumulating most of the Cl remaining in the SRF feedstock after the washing and mild thermal pre-treatment.

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